

Discussion Forum

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Abstract

Online discussion forums are well suited for collaborative learning systems. Much of the currently available research indicates that effectively designed collaborative learning systems motivate and enhance learning experiences of the participants which in turn lead to enhanced learning outcomes. This paper develops taxonomy of the asynchronous online discussion forums with the aims of increasing the understanding and awareness of various types of asynchronous discussion forums. The taxonomy is framed by constructivist pedagogical principles of asynchronous online discussion forum. This paper presents a review of a sample of recent case studies on the use of asynchronous online discussion in higher education. These studies are analyzed in terms of curriculum design, assumptions about

teaching and learning, and claims and reported conditions for using online discussion. This paper discusses the main attitudes of the supporters and opponents of secularization and clericalization both in the Russian Federation, and the wider world. In our understanding, there is a tendency towards secularization in the modern cultural and informational environment. It does not necessarily mean that religion is disappearing; we can see now the rise and fall of the clericalization processes which is a specific situation against the aforementioned general tendency.

1. Introduction

Collaborative learning is based on the idea that learning is a naturally social act in which the learners discuss among themselves and learn from each other. Since the online discussion forums provide the opportunity for students to interact with instructors and each other, the online forums are well suited for collaborative learning. There has been a proliferation of asynchronous online discussion forums in tertiary education. Discussion is usually considered a powerful tool for the development of pedagogical skills such as critical thinking, collaboration and reflection. Rourke and Anderson [34] argue that discussion is an excellent activity for supporting the construction of knowledge, since explaining, elaborating, and defending one's position to others "forces learners to integrate and elaborate knowledge in ways that facilitate higher-order learning". The theme of this paper is teaching and learning through asynchronous online discussion in higher education. The paper reports on case studies in which email lists or conferencing programs such as First Class and WebBoard have been used to support learners who are registered with a higher education institution and, in most cases, following an accredited course.

1.1 What is Discussion Forum?

Discussion forum is a question-and-

answer site where questions are asked, answered, edited, and organized by its community of user's. It is based in Mountain View, California. The company was founded in June 2009, and the website was made available to the public on June 21, 2010.[4] Users can collaborate by editing questions and suggesting edits to answers that have been submitted by other users.[5]

1.2 PROJECT DEFINITION AND PURPOSE

I have built a Simple DF. which is a discussion management system that can be used to dynamically manage the discussion of a simple static HTML website. The main purpose of this project is to have a user-friendly discussion administration interface that includes most common DF functions appropriate for small and simple websites, so that a novice user can manage the forum. A user having less coding knowledge can easily add, edit and format the website's content using the rich text editor integrated in the Simple DF engine without having to deal with the HTML and CSS code.

1.3 Process to use the forum

First fill the form of registration and give some information like email phone number in order to become a unique member of the technical discussion forum. Font page consists of full list of sections, which is called "forums". Out of one of these "forums", you will see a list of forum topics are discussed earlier, each with a unique topic name and it is also provide a description and its "icon".

2. Options of the forum

There are mainly four options are there,
a. The user who is not a registered member can't access the forum, he doesn't have any control on it.

b. The user who is able to login because they are the registered member having full control on forum.

c. Administrator is having the full control on the whole forum and he can see the whole

message and the topic of discussion .he can manage the topic also .

d. The chatting facilities is also available where student can chat their query regarding any topic it is also recommended that no one should do any personal message as everyone can able to see the message.

MODULES:It is mainly consists of six modules like,

1. Home
2. About
3. forum
4. contact
5. message
6. interview

3. Literature Review

Social constructivism assumes that knowledge is actively constructed by the learner [33]. Gilbert and Dabbagh [35] claim that “an important instructional benefit of asynchronous discussion is its potential to support the construction of knowledge’. The use of discussion as a teaching strategy is one way of developing knowledge in a collective environment [40]. Asynchronous online discussion forums have changed the way students have traditionally engaged with course content, with teachers and other students.

3.1 Online Learning and Interactivity

Online learning systems have been described as web based learning environments consisting of digitally formatted content resources via the use of the World Wide Web (Zhu and McKnight, 2001). The online learning system is regarded as a communication device to provide communication link between the instructor and students where they can actively interact (Chang and Fisher, 2001; Piguett and Peraya, 2000).

“Interaction” has been recognized as the most significant attribute in any online system or course (Maor and Volet, 2007; Al-Mahmood and McLoughlin, 2004; Sharples, 2000). Both the conversation theory of learning (Pask, 1975) and social constructive learning theory of learning

with technology (Brown and Campione, 1996) emphasize the fact that learning, to be successful, requires continuous conversation and interaction, not just between teacher and learner, but also amongst the learners. Also learners need time to act and reflect. Consequently, educators should consider interactivity when designing online learning strategies (Maor and Volet, 2007).

Figure 1: Posts by week (Intro to IT)

3.2 Discussion Forums and Participation

The discussion forum is the ubiquitous communication tool within online learning environments and hence significantly shapes the kind of communication that takes place. The asynchronous nature of discussion in a web-based course incorporates interactive communication that is unique and different from face-to-face classroom type instruction and also eliminates the constraints of time and space. Discussion forums have frequently been used successfully as communication tools in online learning environments to facilitate interaction between students to share knowledge (Rovai, 2002) (Bradshaw and Hinton, 2004; Berner, 2003). Discussion forums also provide an effective opportunity to exchange ideas and share knowledge amongst learners and instructors (Tallent-Runnels et al., 2006; Levine, 2007). Because of their potential benefit, online discussion forums are becoming a common feature even in face-to-face courses as they allow students and instructors to communicate with each other regardless of time and space.

3.3 Snap Shot of a Project

Some snap shots of a project are:

Figure 2: Posts by week (Intro to Programming)

4. Methodology

4.1 JAVASCRIPT JavaScript is a client side scripting language designed to add interactivity to HTML pages. A scripting language is a lightweight programming language. It is usually embedded directly into HTML pages. It is an interpreted language which allows the scripts to execute without preliminary compilation.

4.2 PHP PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) is a widely-used open source server-side scripting language for web development and can be embedded into HTML. PHP pages contain HTML with embedded code [23]. PHP offers several advantages:

- PHP runs on different platforms (Windows, Linux, Unix, etc.).
- PHP is compatible with almost all servers used today (Apache, IIS, etc.).
- PHP is free to download from the official PHP resource: www.php.net.
- PHP is easy to learn and runs efficiently on the server side [24].

4.3 HTML

HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) is the set of markup symbols or codes inserted in a file intended for display on a World Wide Web browser page. The markup tells the Web browser how to display a Web page’s words and images for the user. Each individual markup code is referred to as an element (but many people also refer to it as a tag). Some elements come in pairs that indicate when some display effect is to begin and when it is to end.

Source: <https://searchmicroservices.techtarget.com>

4.4 CSS

CSS stands for “Cascading Style Sheet.”

Cascading style sheets are used to format the layout of Web pages. They can be used to define text styles, table sizes, and other aspects of Web pages that previously could only be defined in a page's HTML.

CSS helps Web developers create a uniform look across several pages of a Web site. Instead of defining the style of each table and each block of text within a page's HTML, commonly used styles need to be defined only once in a CSS document.

Source: <https://techterms.com/definition/css>

4.5 Feasibility Study

A feasibility study is an analysis of how successfully a project can be completed, accounting for factors that affect it such as economic, technological, legal and scheduling factors. Project managers use feasibility studies to determine potential positive and negative outcomes of a project before investing a considerable amount of time and money into it.

Source: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/feasibility-study.asp>

CONCLUSION

These papers give useful insight into the nature of and the claims made for asynchronous online discussion, as well as the conditions under which learners are more likely to engage with each other. Researchers express broad agreement that the argument for using asynchronous online discussion rests in a commitment to interaction between learners and adherence to a social constructivist approach to teaching and learning. Interactivity is seen as enabled by the permanent storage of text, accessible anytime from anywhere. Discussion is usually considered a powerful tool for the development of pedagogical skills such as critical thinking, collaboration and reflection. Due to its perceived benefits, asynchronous discussion forums have become progressively popular in tertiary education. The asynchronous online discussion forum offer many pedagogical advantages such as encouraging reflection, analysis and high order thinking.

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